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CA' FOSCARI UNIVERSITY OF VENICE (ITALY)

Book of Abstracts

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Executive Board of the European Chemical Society, I wish you a warm welcome to this 18th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment. The European Chemical Society – in short EuChemS – is an overarching society at the European level with over 50 national member societies as members. In this way, EuChemS represents approximately 130,000 chemists from all over Europe. Did you ever realize that by being a member of your national society, you are a member of EuChemS too?

The slogan of this conference is 'Towards a pollution free society', which is well aligned with activities from EuChemS. The European Commission recently set up the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform and EuChemS was invited to join. The platform will effectively mainstream the zero pollution agenda by bringing together stakeholders and experts of different policy areas, including health, agriculture, research and innovation, transport, digitalization and the environment. EuChemS will emphasize to address the Zero Pollution challenges from the chemistry perspective in a science-based approach.

I am here in the Netherlands, but you are in the beautiful city of Venice, that I am sure will inspire you to have fruitful and constructive discussions on how to get to zero pollution and how to address many other challenges to create a sustainable environment. I wish you a very enjoyable conference!

Floris Rutjens

President of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS)

Multicentric Study of Urban Air Quality in Vojvodina (Serbia) and Assessment of Associated Carcinogenic Risk

S. Bobić^{1*}, Lj. Torović^{1,2}, D. Lukić¹, M. Jovanović¹, N. Stanojković¹ and S. Bijelović^{1,2}

¹Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Center for Hygiene and Human Ecology, Futoska 121, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

stanka.bobic@izjzv.org.rs

Ambient air pollution in urban areas represents one of prime concerns regarding adverse health effects. The aim of this study was to assess air quality as well as carcinogenic risk due to inhalation exposure to lead, cadmium, nickel, arsenic and benzo(a)pyrene bound to PM₁₀ in ambient air of four major cities in Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia. The data applied were obtained by official air quality monitoring and include data from 2021 and 2022. Fixed measurements were conducted at the locations classified as urban traffic (Novi Sad and Zrenjanin), and urban background (Kikinda and Sombor) in accordance with Directive 2008/50/EC (European Commission, 2008). Obtained results showed that mean annual levels of PM₁₀ were slightly higher on urban traffic (Novi Sad/Zrenjanin 30/39 µg/m³ in 2021, and 36/38 µg/m³ in 2022) compared to urban background locations (Kikinda/Sombor 30/27 µg/m³ in 2021, and 31/23 µg/m³ in 2022), but all remained under the limit value. Oppositely, daily PM₁₀ limit value was exceeded more frequently than allowed, i.e., in 37, 65 and 37 days in Novi Sad, Zrenjanin and Kikinda, respectively, in 2021, and in 2022 in 49 and 54 days in Novi Sad and Zrenjanin, respectively. Mean annual levels of measured toxic metals did not exceed the limit value in any of the cities, whereas in case of benzo(a)pyrene the annual target value was surpassed in 2021 in all cities (max annual mean 2.4 ng/m³ in Sombor), and in 2022 only in Sombor (1.1 ng/m³). Although below the target value, the annual levels of benzo(a)pyrene on other locations in 2022, ranging from 0.9-1.0 ng/m³, should be considered as a warning. The obtained results were exploited for inhalation health risk assessment. The carcinogenic risk assessment carried out according to OEHHA (OEHHA, 2015) guidance, considered differences of daily breathing rate, body weight, age sensitivity and exposure duration. At all cities, increased carcinogenic risk (ICR) for children (<16 years) related to lead exposure was lower than 1x10⁻⁶, the level considered as the limit of acceptability according to US EPA guidelines (USEPA, 2005), while ICR related to cadmium, nickel, arsenic and benzo(a)pyrene exposure was higher than 1x10⁻⁶. For adults (16-70 years) exposed to arsenic and benzo(a)pyrene, ICR was between 1x10⁻⁶ and 1x10⁻⁴, till ICR derived from exposure to other toxic metals was below the acceptable level. The highest carcinogenic risk in all age groups was attributed to arsenic (children, up to 1x10⁻⁵; adults, up to 4.9x10⁻⁶) in each measuring site. Such results should prompt undertaking of appropriate management measures.

References

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